

An efficient and mild superoxide induced Michael addition of indoles to α,β -unsaturated ketones

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Abstract : A facile Michael addition of indoles to electron-deficient olefins has been accomplished in the presence of tetraethylammonium superoxide at room temperature in reasonably good yields. The substitution on the indole ring occurred exclusively at 3-position without a trace of any *N*-alkylated products.

Keywords : Michael addition, superoxide ion, indole, α,β -unsaturated ketone.

Introduction

The development of synthetic methods leading to indole derivatives has attracted much attention in organic synthesis because of their biological activities¹. Various indoles are components of drugs and manifest potent antibacterial and antimycotic activities². Among them, 3-substituted indolylketones are important building blocks for the synthesis of many natural products such as indolyl alkaloid, hapalindole D³. Michael reaction of indole with α,β -unsaturated ketones giving 3-(3-oxoalkyl)indole or β -indolylketones is an important carbon-carbon bond forming reaction. Considering the importance of 3-(3-oxoalkyl)indoles, a number of methods have been described for their synthesis using various catalysts such as protic acids⁴, Lewis acids⁵, acidic clay⁶, inorganic salts⁷, iodine⁸, basic Al₂O₃⁹, organocatalyst¹⁰, nitrosonium¹¹, ionic liquids¹², heteropoly acid¹³, PVSA¹⁴, bimetallic catalyst¹⁵, FAP¹⁶, TCT¹⁷ and silica gel¹⁸. However, many of these methods suffer from drawbacks, such as drastic reaction conditions, long reaction times and low yields of products due to dimerization of indoles or polymerization of the unsaturated acceptors under acid-catalyzed conditions.

In view of the above and as a part of our ongoing research on superoxide organic chemistry¹⁹, we report

herein remarkable activity of tetraethylammonium superoxide for the conjugate addition of indoles to α,β -unsaturated ketones at room temperature, providing an efficient and mild synthesis of β -indolylketones (Scheme 1).

In the present course of reaction, tetraethylammonium superoxide (Et₄NO₂) was generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide in dry DMF at room temperature. The resulting superoxide is then allowed to react with indole (**1a**) or 2-methylindole (**1b**) in the presence of a variety of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds **2a-e** to afford 3-(3-oxoalkyl)indoles (**3a-i**) in reasonably good yields at room temperature. In order to optimize the yield of the product, the reaction was tried in a number of organic aprotic solvents and DMF was found to be the best in all respects.

The reaction was accomplished by using a two fold molar excess of KO₂ and equimolar ratio of Et₄NBr with respect to the substrate **1**. Generally, the reaction was completed in 3.0–5.5 h at room temperature. The reaction was then quenched with cold brine solution and worked up to isolate the product. The total disappearance of the starting material was checked by thin-layer chromatography (TLC). The reactions were clean and the products were obtained in high yields without the formation

Scheme 1

of any *N*-alkylated side product. All the products were fully identified by their physical and spectral data, which were in full agreement with their structures.

Experimental

Potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide were procured from E. Merck and were used as received. Dry DMF of Aldrich was stored over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to its use. Indole, 2-methylindole and methyl vinyl ketone were purchased from Aldrich, whereas chalcones were prepared according to the literature procedure²⁰. Melting points were measured in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrometer. NMR was run on a JEOL AL300 FT-NMR spectrometer and the chemical shifts are given in δ (ppm) with respect to TMS as internal reference. The TLC spots were detected using iodine chamber. Crude products were purified by column chromatography.

Michael addition of indoles to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds : *General procedure* :

Potassium superoxide (0.28 g, 4 mmol) and tetraethylammonium bromide (0.42 g, 2 mmol) were weighed under nitrogen atmosphere using an atmosbag and were transferred into a three necked round bottom flask fitted with a dropping funnel, magnetic stirrer, nitrogen inlet and a condenser protected by calcium chloride drying tube. Dry DMF (15 mL) was added to it and the mixture was stirred

for 15 min to facilitate the formation of Et₄NO₂. To the stirred reaction mixture was added dropwise a mixture of indole (2 mmol) and unsaturated ketone (2 mmol) dissolved in dry DMF. Nitrogen was bubbled continuously and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3.0 to 5.5 h at room temperature until the reaction was completed (TLC). After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was successively treated with brine solution (10 mL) and aqueous saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (10 mL) and then extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 \times 20 mL). The combined organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and evaporated to give the crude product, which was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluted with ethyl acetate : *n*-hexane = 1 : 9) to afford the pure product **3a-i**.

(3a) Yield : 71%; m.p. 70–71 °C (lit.^{5c} 71–72 °C); IR (KBr) : 3405, 2927, 1710, 1356, 1162, 745 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.13 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.81 (2H, t, CH₂), 3.08 (2H, t, CH₂), 6.91 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.18 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.21 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.33 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.58 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.80 (1H, brs, NH).

(3b) Colourless viscous oil^{5c}; yield : 65%; IR (neat) : 3407, 3034, 2925, 1713, 1458, 1371, 1222, 1172, 748 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.08 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.79 (2H, t, CH₂), 3.06 (2H, t, CH₂), 7.07–7.16 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.39–7.41 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, brs, NH).

(3c) Yield : 67%; m.p. 127–129 °C (lit.¹¹ 127–128 °C);

IR (KBr) : 3402, 3047, 2923, 1678, 1459, 1374, 743 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.63–3.74 (2H, m, CH_2), 5.03 (1H, t, CH), 7.03–7.12 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.29–7.43 (10H, m, Ar-H), 7.76 (1H, brs, NH), 7.85–7.91 (2H, m, Ar-H).

(3d) Yield : 64%; m.p. 118 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3407, 3039, 2955, 1675, 1598, 1453, 1371, 734 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.59–3.66 (2H, m, CH_2), 5.05 (1H, t, CH), 6.97–7.07 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.18–7.31 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.38–7.43 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.47–7.51 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.79 (1H, brs, NH), 7.83–7.87 (2H, m, Ar-H).

(3e) Yield : 68%; m.p. 123–124 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3405, 3037, 2959, 1677, 1595, 1451, 1372, 745 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.81 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.87–3.95 (2H, m, CH_2), 5.07 (1H, t, CH), 6.83 (2H, d, Ar-H), 6.91–7.01 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.16–7.18 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.26–7.31 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.43–7.50 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, brs, NH), 7.85 (2H, d, Ar-H).

(3f) Yield : 63%; m.p. 111 $^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.^{5c} 110 $^\circ\text{C}$); IR (KBr) : 3409, 3038, 2957, 1676, 1593, 1448, 1375, 746 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.43 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.81–3.90 (2H, m, CH_2), 5.06 (1H, t, CH), 6.81 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.01–7.08 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.13–7.16 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.27–7.33 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.39 (2H, t, Ar-H), 7.47–7.54 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, brs, NH), 7.88 (2H, d, Ar-H).

(3g) Yield : 61% m.p. 141–142 $^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.^{5c} 140 $^\circ\text{C}$); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.81–3.89 (2H, m, CH_2), 5.23 (1H, t, CH), 7.04–7.11 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.21 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.36–7.48 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.59 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.79 (1H, d, Ar-H), 8.02 (1H, d, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, d, Ar-H), 8.11 (1H, brs, NH), 8.21 (2H, d, Ar-H).

(3h) Yield : 60%; m.p. 140 $^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.^{5c} 138 $^\circ\text{C}$); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.47 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.91 (2H, d, CH_2), 5.21 (1H, t, CH), 7.02–7.07 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.23 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.35–7.43 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.51 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.83 (1H, brs, NH), 7.89 (2H, d, Ar-H), 8.03 (1H, d, Ar-H), 8.18 (1H, s, Ar-H).

(3i) Yield : 65%; m.p. 122–124 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3409, 3031, 2956, 1673, 1591, 1450, 1374, 747 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.80–3.87

(2H, m, CH_2), 5.09 (1H, t, CH), 6.86 (2H, d, Ar-H), 6.96–7.11 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, brs, NH), 7.76–7.87 (7H, m, Ar-H).

Conclusion :

In conclusion, the present report offers a facile way to prepare 3-(3-oxoalkyl)indoles by the addition of indole or 2-methylindole to a variety of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds under significantly mild reaction conditions at room temperature.

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